

Chemical Profiling and Structure-Based Virtual Screening of Ukrainian Propolis Reveals Polyphenolic Compounds with Potential Activity against New Delhi Metallo- β -Lactamase-1

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Abstract

The global escalation of bacterial resistance to β -lactam antibiotics, primarily driven by the production of β -lactamase enzymes, represents a critical threat to public health. This study explores the potential of Ukrainian steppe bee propolis as a natural source of inhibitors targeting New Delhi metallo- β -lactamase-1 (NDM-1). Using high-performance liquid chromatography coupled with tandem mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS), we identified a complex mixture of polyphenolic compounds, including pinocembrin, galangin, chrysin, and caffeic acid esters.

In silico drug-likeness assessments based on the Lipinski, Veber, and Egan criteria demonstrated that these propolis-derived compounds occupy a favorable physicochemical space characterized by moderate lipophilicity and low polar

surface area, suggesting improved potential for oral bioavailability compared to many clinically used β -lactamase inhibitors.

Molecular docking simulations performed against the NDM-1 crystal structure (PDB ID: 8I8F) revealed that several natural compounds exhibit binding affinities stronger than those of established inhibitors such as tazobactam and avibactam. Notably, pinocembrin (-7.419 kcal/mol) and galangin (-7.395 kcal/mol) emerged as lead candidates, demonstrating stable interactions within the enzyme's catalytic cavity in proximity to the active-site Zn^{2+} ions.

These findings highlight Ukrainian propolis as a rich reservoir of bioactive scaffolds that may serve as effective adjuncts in antimicrobial therapy to combat β -lactam resistance.

1. Introduction

β -lactams are among the most widely used antibiotics in medical practice, accounting for approximately 50% of all prescriptions worldwide (Fan et al., 2025). These antibiotics are characterized by a four-membered saturated ring containing one nitrogen and three carbon atoms. The β -lactam ring, when functionalized with different substituents, serves as an intermediate in the synthesis of peptides, derivatives of aromatic amino acids, polyamine esters, and other compounds (Garg et al., 2024). As antibacterial agents, β -lactams mimic natural substrates to inhibit

cell wall biosynthesis, specifically by blocking transpeptidase-mediated cross-linking of peptidoglycan strands (Yang et al., 2025). However, the emergence and spread of bacterial resistance to β -lactams and other antibiotics pose a significant global threat to the environment and public health (Aslam et al., 2018; Dou et al., 2022; Canabal et al., 2024).

The primary mechanism of bacterial resistance to β -lactam antibiotics is the biosynthesis of β -lactamase enzymes, which deactivate the antibiotic by hydrolyzing the amide bond in its β -lactam ring (Ma et al., 2022; Khanna et al., 2022). β -lactamase enzymes are classified into four groups (A-D) based on similarities in their DNA sequences. Classes A, C, and D utilize an active site serine residue as a nucleophile, while class B enzymes rely on a Zn(II)-bound hydroxide anion for their catalytic activity. Metallo- β -lactamases (MBLs), part of class B, are further divided into three subclasses: B1, B2, and B3. Subclass B2 is mono-zinc-dependent, while subclasses B1 and B3 are predominantly di-zinc-dependent enzymes. MBLs are considered the most significant threat in the development of resistance to β -lactam antibiotics (Canabal et al., 2024; Khanna et al., 2022).

Given the critical role of β -lactamases in antibiotic resistance, the search for effective inhibitors of these enzymes remains an urgent priority. β -lactamase inhibitors are molecules capable of binding to the enzyme's active site, thereby protecting the antibiotic from hydrolysis. Such inhibitors can have β -lactam

structures, as exemplified by clavulanic acid, the first clinically used β -lactamase inhibitor (Khanna et al., 2022; Kang et al., 2024). However, inhibitory activity has also been reported for compounds containing other heterocyclic and aromatic rings (Yahav et al., 2020; Haque et al., 2024), including those of polyphenolic nature (Houchi et al., 2019). Despite advancements in β -lactamase inhibitor research, the discovery of novel and effective inactivators of these enzymes remains a pressing medical challenge.

Natural sources, which are rich in biologically active compounds and exhibit diverse pharmacological effects, have garnered significant attention. These natural products offer advantages such as minimal side effects and widespread availability (Talati et al., 2024). For instance, the health benefits of apicultural products are well-documented. Propolis, a key product, exhibits anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, antitumor, and antimicrobial properties (Pratami et al., 2024). Its antimicrobial activity includes the potential inhibition of β -lactamases, as evidenced by the enhanced efficacy of β -lactam antibiotics in the presence of propolis extracts (Ripari et al., 2023). This mixed biological activity is largely attributed to its mixture of polyphenolic compounds (Widelski et al., 2023).

However, despite the well-known effects of propolis, the specific active compounds and their mechanisms of action remain poorly understood. The composition of propolis is largely determined by regional plant biodiversity. In east

of Ukraine, native species such as *Crataegus ucrainica* and others have been identified in the Svydnyia River valley (Schevchyk et al., 2021), underscoring the ecological uniqueness of the flora available to foraging bees. The lack of standardization in propolis production leads to variations in its qualitative and quantitative composition, making it challenging to predict and evaluate its biological activity. Additionally, the components of propolis are believed to act synergistically (Bouchelaghem et al., 2022). Thus, there is a need for a more detailed investigation of the roles of individual propolis components in their pharmacological effects. The aim of this study was to determine the component composition of propolis synthesized by a colony of Ukrainian steppe bees and to conduct molecular docking of its components to identify potential β -lactamase inhibitors.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Sample Collection and Chromatographic Separation

Aqueous propolis extracts were obtained from hives of Ukrainian steppe bees. Components were separated using high-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) (Das et al., 2022). Chromatography was conducted on a Zorbax C18 SB300 9.4 × 250 mm column (Agilent Technologies, 5988-2092EN), with a 30-minute runtime and linear gradients as follows:

Solvent A: 98% → 30% ddH₂O with 0.1% trifluoroacetic acid (TFA)

Solvent B: 1.95% → 71.25% acetonitrile (100%)

Solvent C: 0.05% → 3.75% ddH₂O with 1.7% TFA

The column temperature was maintained at 25 °C, and the elution rate was 1.0 mL/min. Protein fraction separation followed the manufacturer's protocol.

2.2. Mass Detection and Compound Identification

Compounds were identified using liquid chromatography–mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) (Balingui et al., 2019). Analyses were performed in negative ion mode over m/z 100–1500 at 3.0 spectra/s. Ion source conditions included a capillary voltage of 4 kV, source temperature of 325 °C, nitrogen gas at 35 psi and 12 L/min flow. Octapole RF and fragmentor voltages were set at –750 V and 350 V, respectively.

MS/MS fragmentation was performed in all-ion mode using 10, 20, and 30 eV collision energies. Data were processed using Agilent MassHunter (v10.0). Spectral identification was based on comparisons with the Personal Compound Database Library (score >80%, mass error <5 ppm). Fragmentation patterns were validated in silico using ACD/Spectrus Processor (Lopez-Rodulfo et al., 2024).

2.3. Drug-likeness Assessment (Lipinski, Veber, and Egan Rules)

Drug-likeness and physicochemical suitability of the investigated compounds were evaluated using the Lipinski, Veber, and Egan filter criteria. SMILES structures for all ligands were processed in RDKit (<https://www.rdkit.org>) to calculate core molecular descriptors, including molecular weight (MW), octanol/water partition coefficient (logP), number of hydrogen bond donors (HBD) and acceptors (HBA), number of rotatable bonds (RotB), and topological polar surface area (TPSA).

Lipinski's Rule of Five was used to assess general oral drug-likeness based on thresholds $MW \leq 500$ Da, $\log P \leq 5$, $HBD \leq 5$, and $HBA \leq 10$. Veber's rule was applied to evaluate oral bioavailability using $RotB \leq 10$ and $TPSA \leq 140 \text{ \AA}^2$. Egan's filter was used to assess passive permeability and intestinal absorption (criteria: $TPSA \leq 130 \text{ \AA}^2$ and $-1 \leq \log P \leq 5.8$). Results were confirmed using SwissADME server (<https://www.swissadme.ch>) (Daina et al., 2017).

2.4. Computational Docking Workflow

Molecular docking was used to evaluate the binding affinity of propolis-derived compounds toward New Delhi metallo- β -lactamase-1 (NDM 1; PDB ID: 8I8F (Shi et al., 2024)). All analyses were scripted in a local Jupyter Notebook environment (<https://jupyter.org>).

The NDM 1 crystal structure was obtained from the RCSB Protein Data Bank (<https://www.rcsb.org>) and prepared using `prepare_receptor4.py` from MGLTools (Scripps Research, 2009; Sanner, 1999). Receptor preparation included isolation of chain A, removal of water molecules and co-crystallized ligand, and conversion to PDBQT format.

Ligand structures, imported from a CSV file containing SMILES strings, were converted into 3D conformers and geometry-optimized using RDKit (<https://www.rdkit.org>). Structures were then converted to PDBQT format using Open Babel (O'Boyle et al., 2011), ensuring correct protonation and atom typing.

Docking grids were defined based on the spatial center of the native ligand, with a 5 Å padding in each dimension, calculated using NumPy. Docking simulations were performed using AutoDock Vina (Trott et al., 2010; Eberhardt et al., 2021) with an exhaustiveness of 32. For each ligand, the pose with the lowest predicted binding free energy was retained. Docking results were ranked by ascending binding energy, and protein–ligand interactions were visualized and examined using Py3Dmol.

3. Results

3.1. Separation and Identification of Propolis Extract Components

The object of study was a 2% aqueous solution of propolis extract obtained from Ukrainian steppe bees. Chromatographic separation (Figure 1) revealed a complex mixture of polyphenolic compounds. These were identified via LC–MS/MS analysis by comparing their spectra to literature-reported values (Kasote et al., 2014; Donmez et al., 2020).

Table 1 summarizes the retention times, m/z values, MS² fragmentation, and classification of the key identified compounds. Flavonoids—including pinocembrin 5-methyl ether, chrysin, galangin, and dimethyl ether of quercetin—dominated the extract profile. In addition, hydroxycinnamic acid derivatives such as isoprenyl and phenethyl ethers of caffeic acid were detected.

Table 1. Identification of main compounds in Ukrainian propolis extract by LC–MS/MS, including retention time, m/z values, fragment ions, and classification.

Retention Time (Rt), min	[M-H] ⁻ m/z	MS ²	Identified Compound	Compound Class
25.7	285	252, 224, 267, 195, 239, 165, 138	Pinobanksin 5-methyl ether	Flavonoid (flavonone)
27.4	271	197, 253, 125, 161, 225	Pinobanksin (or vestitol, or neovestitol)	Flavonoid (flavonone)
53.6	255	171, 151, 213, 185	Pinocembrin	Flavonoid (flavonone)

55.4	329	299, 271, 314	Dimethyl ether of quercetin	Flavonoid (dimethoxyflavone, flavonone)	
56.6	247	133	Isoprenyl ether of caffeic acid	Derivative hydroxycinnamic acid	of
57.4	253	209, 143, 181	Chrysin	Flavonoid (flavonone)	
58.4	269	169, 195, 197, 211, 213, 223, 227, 238, 241	Galangin	Flavonoid (flavonol)	
59,7	283	133, 135, 161, 179	Phenethyl ether of caffeic acid	Derivative hydroxycinnamic acid	of

The analysis of the qualitative composition of the propolis extract revealed the presence of several notable compounds, which were identified and unequivocally confirmed through liquid chromatography with mass-selective detection (LC-MS/MS). The identified compounds included pinocembrin 5-methyl ether, pinocembrin, dimethyl ether of quercetin, chrysin, galangin, as well as isoprenyl and phenethyl ethers of caffeic acid. These compounds represent a diverse group of bioactive molecules, each with its distinct structural characteristics and potential pharmacological properties.

In addition to these compounds, a pseudomolecular ion with a mass-to-charge ratio ($[M-H]^-$) of 271 m/z was detected in the propolis extract. This ion was accompanied by its ionization products, which included m/z values of 253, 225, 197,

161, and 125. The presence of this ion and its associated fragments points to the possible co-existence of multiple isomeric compounds in the sample. Specifically, these mass-detection values may correspond to pinobanksin, vestitol, and neovestitol. These compounds share structural similarities as isomers, making it challenging to distinguish between them based solely on their mass-spectrometric characteristics.

Pinobanksin, vestitol, and neovestitol belong to the flavonoid class of compounds, which are well-known for their diverse biological activities, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial properties. However, due to their isomeric nature, these compounds cannot be definitively identified using the current analytical methods. The overlap in their mass spectrometric signals necessitates additional studies to achieve accurate separation and precise detection. Such studies could involve advanced chromatographic techniques, such as chiral chromatography, or complementary analytical methods, such as nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectroscopy.

The results presented in Table 1 summarize the retention times, mass-to-charge ratios, fragmentation patterns, and classification of the identified compounds. For example, pinocembrin-5-methyl ether exhibited a retention time of 25.7 minutes, with a [M-H]⁻ m/z of 285 and fragment ions at m/z 252, 224, 267, 195, 239, 165, and 138. This compound belongs to the flavonoid class, specifically the flavanone

subclass, which is known for its antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties. Similarly, dimethyl ether of quercetin, detected at a retention time of 55.4 minutes with an m/z of 329, represents another significant flavonoid, classified as a dimethoxyflavone. This compound is notable for its potential as an anti-inflammatory agent due to its polyphenolic structure.

Pinobanksin

Caffeic acid isoprenyl ester

Chrysin

Quercetin dimethyl ether

Pinocembrin

Vestitol

Galangin

Neovestitol

Caffeic acid phenethyl ester

Figure 1. Molecular structures of representative compounds identified in the Ukrainian propolis extract.

Chrysin, detected at 57.4 minutes with an m/z of 253, is another flavanone known for its potential anticancer and anti-inflammatory effects. Galangin, identified at 58.4 minutes with an m/z of 269, is a flavonol with significant antibacterial and antioxidant properties. The hydroxycinnamic acid derivatives, including isoprenyl ether of caffeic acid ($R_t = 56.6$ min, $m/z = 247$) and phenethyl ether of caffeic acid ($R_t = 59.7$ min, $m/z = 283$), also add to the biological relevance of the propolis extract. These derivatives are well-known for their antioxidant activities and potential protective effects against various diseases.

Overall, the qualitative composition analysis highlights the complexity and richness of the propolis extract in bioactive compounds. The detection of flavonoids, such as pinocembrin and galangin, alongside hydroxycinnamic acid derivatives, underscores the potential of this natural product as a source of therapeutic agents. However, the isomeric nature of some detected compounds, such as pinobanksin, vestitol, and neovestitol, presents an analytical challenge that requires further investigation using advanced methodologies to ensure accurate identification and characterization. These findings provide a foundation for future research into the pharmacological properties and potential applications of propolis in medicine.

3.2. Drug-Likeness Evaluation of Known β -Lactamase Inhibitors and Propolis-Derived Compounds

Drug-likeness evaluation serves as an early screening tool to predict whether a bioactive compound has physicochemical properties compatible with oral drug development. Common guidelines like Lipinski's Rule of Five (Ro5) set threshold values (e.g. molecular weight ≤ 500 Da, $\log P \leq 5$, H-bond donors ≤ 5 , H-bond acceptors ≤ 10) beyond which oral absorption tends to drop off. A compound with no more than one Ro5 violation is more likely to achieve sufficient oral bioavailability, thus lowering the risk of failure in later development (Lambeve et al., 2025). These criteria, along with related filters (Veber's rule for polar surface area and rotatability, Egan's filter for permeability), provide a framework for assessing ADME-friendliness, ensuring that promising molecules also possess the fundamental traits of an orally active drug.

A well-known BLIs and propolis-derived compounds in this study fall within drug-like chemical space as defined by Lipinski and Veber criteria. Molecular size is comparable between the two groups: both span roughly 200–350 Da, well under the 500 Da cutoff. Accordingly, none of the compounds violate Lipinski's molecular weight, H-bonding, or lipophilicity parameters (zero Ro5 violations in all cases). They also meet Veber's guideline (topological polar surface area (TPSA) $< 140 \text{ \AA}^2$ and rotatable bonds ≤ 10) predictive of good oral bioavailability (Lagorce et al.,

2015). This across-the-board compliance indicates that both the clinical inhibitors and the propolis phytochemicals possess fundamentally drug-like profiles, at least by classical descriptors.

Table 2. Drug-Likeness Parameters of Known β -Lactamase Inhibitors and Propolis-Derived Compounds.

Compound	MW	logP	HBD	HBA	RotB	TPSA	Lipinski violations	Fit to Lipinski rules	Fit to Veber rules	Fit to Egan rule
Clavulanate	199.162	-1.0956	2	4	2	87.07	0	True	True	False
Sulbactam	233.245	-0.795	1	4	1	91.75	0	True	True	True
Tazobactam	300.296	-1.5232	1	7	3	122.46	0	True	True	False
Avibactam	265.247	-1.5253	2	5	3	130.24	0	True	True	False
Durlobactam	277.258	-1.3592	2	5	3	130.24	0	True	True	False
Relebactam	348.381	-1.1424	3	6	4	128.28	0	True	True	False
Pinocembrin	256.257	2.8043	2	4	1	66.76	0	True	True	True
Quercetin dimethyl ether	330.292	2.594	3	7	3	109.36	0	True	True	True
Chrysin	254.241	2.8712	2	4	1	70.67	0	True	True	True
Galangin	270.24	2.5768	3	5	1	90.9	0	True	True	True
Caffeic acid phenethyl ester	300.31	3.681	2	4	6	75.99	0	True	True	True
Caffeic acid isoprenyl ester	246.262	2.744	2	4	4	66.76	0	True	True	True
Pinobanksin	272.256	1.7751	3	5	1	86.99	0	True	True	True
Vestitol	272.3	2.8251	2	4	2	58.92	0	True	True	True
Neovestitol	272.3	2.8251	2	4	2	58.92	0	True	True	True
Captopril	217.29	0.6279	2	3	3	57.61	0	True	True	True

Despite this overall similarity, distinctive differences emerge in polarity and flexibility. The marketed β -lactamase inhibitors are highly polar molecules: for example, avibactam and relebactam carry acidic sulfate or sulfonamide groups, yielding calculated logP values around -1 to -1.5 and elevated TPSA (~ 120 – 130 Å²). Such extreme hydrophilicity contrasts with the propolis-derived compounds, which are moderately lipophilic (logP ~ 2 – 3) and have lower TPSA (mostly 60 – 110 Å²). In fact, most of the BLI drugs fall just outside the optimal polarity range defined by Egan's filter (ideal $-1 \leq \log P \leq 5.8$, $TPSA \leq 130$) (Lagorce et al., 2015). Avibactam, for instance, has $\log P \approx -1.5$ and $TPSA \sim 130$ Å², slightly exceeding Egan's polarity bounds, consistent with its need for intravenous administration (Gordon et al., 2018). By contrast, a representative propolis flavonoid like pinocembrin (MW 256, logP ~ 2.8 , TPSA ~ 67 Å²) lies comfortably within these ranges, reflecting a more balanced polarity for passive membrane permeability. All propolis compounds examined carry 2–3 hydroxyl or phenolic donor groups and 4–7 hydrogen-bond acceptors, similar to the moderate H-bond counts in the drug inhibitors, but without the charge-extreme functional groups of the synthetic BLIs. Structurally, the flavonoid-type propolis molecules (pinocembrin, chrysin, galangin, etc.) are rigid polyaromatic frameworks with very few rotatable bonds (often only 1), whereas the BLI scaffolds (penam sulfones and diazabicyclooctanes) are bicyclic/bridged systems that also limit rotatable bonds to about 1–4. An outlier

among the natural set is caffeic acid phenethyl ester (CAPE), a flexible phenylpropanoid ester with ~6 rotatable bonds, yet its PSA (~76 Å²) remains low. In summary, the propolis-derived compounds occupy a slightly more hydrophobic and aromatic-rich region of chemical space compared to the polar, heterocycle-rich β -lactamase inhibitors, while both groups maintain favorable molecular size and hydrogen-bonding profiles. This observation aligns with reports that certain propolis flavonoids exhibit inherent drug-like properties, making them suitable candidates for further development.

The stark polarity differences have practical implications for oral bioavailability. Most clinically used BLIs are so polar that they are not orally absorbed and must be delivered parenterally. Indeed, clavulanic acid (1984) remains the only FDA-approved β -lactamase inhibitor available for oral use parenterally (Gordon et al., 2018). The hydrophilic, anionic character (reflected in negative logP values) limits transmembrane uptake in the gut. In contrast, the propolis-derived compounds, with their moderate lipophilicity and lack of permanent charges, are poised to have far better passive absorption. Such pharmacokinetic behavior underscores that these natural products can achieve bioactive exposure levels when administered orally, an encouraging sign if they are to be developed as systemic therapeutics.

The propolis compounds offer a promising advantage: many are polyphenolic frameworks capable of metal-chelation or otherwise interfering with metallo-

enzymes. Recent studies have identified several natural polyphenols as potential NDM-1 inhibitors. For instance, the flavonol morin was shown to bind and inhibit NDM-1, restoring carbapenem efficacy in NDM-1 producing bacteria (4–32-fold minimum inhibitory concentration reductions when combined with β -lactams). Morin on its own lacked direct antibiotic activity, but in combination it suppressed NDM-1-mediated resistance, thereby laying groundwork for flavonoid-based NDM-1 inhibitors (Ren et al., 2025). Similarly, in-silico screening has singled out compounds like butein (a chalcone), monodemethylcurcumin (a curcuminoid), and rosmarinic acid (a caffeic acid dimer) as micromolar inhibitors of NDM-1, with each showing high predicted oral absorption and zero Lipinski rule violations (Bibi et al., 2023). Notably, these hits share a family resemblance to the propolis-derived flavonoids and phenolic esters under evaluation here. Even the dietary flavonol quercetin (structurally similar to galangin and quercetin dimethyl ether) has demonstrated β -lactamase inhibitory effects, synergizing with amoxicillin against resistant *Staphylococcus* by blocking its β -lactamase activity (Cael et al., 2016). Such evidence suggests that the propolis compounds, by virtue of occupying a different physicochemical niche (less polar, polyphenolic scaffolds), could engage β -lactamase targets. The propolis compounds reside in a more lipophilic and aromatic space, retaining drug-like size and flexibility, which correlates with better membrane permeability and oral drug potential (Shen et al., 2019).

3.3. Molecular Docking of New Delhi Metallo- β -Lactamase (NDM-1) with Propolis Components

Molecular docking simulations were conducted to evaluate the binding affinities of identified propolis-derived polyphenolic compounds with the crystal structure of New Delhi Metallo- β -Lactamase (NDM-1; PDB ID: 8I8F). Several clinically validated β -lactamase inhibitors, including avibactam, tazobactam, relebactam, durlobactam, clavulanate, sulbactam, and captopril, were included for comparative analysis.

Among the tested compounds, pinocembrin exhibited the strongest binding affinity (-7.419 kcal/mol), followed closely by galangin (-7.395 kcal/mol). These values surpassed those of known inhibitors, including Tazobactam (-5.448 kcal/mol), Avibactam (-6.216 kcal/mol), and durlobactam (-5.783 kcal/mol). Other natural compounds such as neovestitol, chrysin, isoprenyl ether of caffeic acid, pinobanksin, and vestitol also demonstrated notable docking scores, suggesting promising interaction capabilities with the enzyme's active site.

Table 3. Docking results of natural propolis-derived compounds and known β -lactamase inhibitors against chain A of NDM-1 (PDB ID: 8I8F), ranked by binding free energy.

Ligand Name	Binding Free Energy (kcal/mol)
Pinocembrin	-7.419
Galangin	-7.395
Neovestitol	-7.034
Chrysin	-6.998
Caffeic acid phenethyl ester	-6.932
Pinobanksin	-6.928
Vestitol	-6.917
Quercetin dimethyl ether	-6.629
Relebactam	-6.556
Caffeic acid isoprenyl ester	-6.431
Avibactam	-6.216
Durlobactam	-5.783
Tazobactam	-5.448
Clavulanic acid	-5.274
Sulbactam	-5.174
Captopril	-4.978

The full docking results are summarized in Table 3. In addition to high-affinity binding energies, several of the top-scoring compounds share structural features

typical of flavonoids and hydroxycinnamic acid derivatives, which are known for their antimicrobial properties.

Pinocembrin, a flavanone widely present in propolis, has been extensively studied for its therapeutic potential. It exhibits antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, antimicrobial, and neuroprotective properties. Despite other properties, in vitro studies have shown that pinocembrin inhibits the growth of *Staphylococcus aureus*, including methicillin-resistant strains, making it a promising natural antibacterial agent (Elbatreek et al., 2023). Moreover, pinocembrin's low toxicity and favorable pharmacokinetics have positioned it as a candidate for development against microbial infections and inflammatory conditions.

Docking-based interaction analysis revealed that pinocembrin is positioned within the NDM-1 active site in proximity to both catalytic Zn^{2+} ions. The ligand shows two direct metal-contact distances ($Zn-O \approx 2.5-2.6 \text{ \AA}$), indicating that the phenolic oxygen atoms lie within the first coordination sphere of Zn^{2+} . This places pinocembrin close enough to interact with the metal center, although no clear bidentate chelation geometry is observed.

Figure 2 Molecular interactions of pinocembrin within the active site of chain A of NDM-1 (PDB ID: 8I8F). (a) Coordination of pinocembrin with zinc ions; (b) Interactions of pinocembrin with surrounding amino acid residues.

In addition to the metal contacts, the ligand forms several polar or hydrogen-bond-like interactions within 3.0–3.5 Å. These include contacts with His189, His122, Asp124, Asn220 and Lys211, as well as multiple short-distance interactions involving a crystallographic water molecule (HOH410). While the exact hydrogen-bonding geometry cannot be confirmed from docking alone, these distances indicate that pinocembrin is positioned within a polar environment shaped by these residues.

The interaction profile also contains numerous hydrophobic contacts within 3.1–4.0 Å involving Leu65, Met67, Phe70, Val73 and Trp93. These nonpolar residues appear to form a hydrophobic pocket around the ligand's aromatic scaffold, contributing to its stabilization in the binding cavity.

Overall, the docking-derived contact map suggests that pinocembrin interacts with the NDM-1 active site through a combination of (i) close contacts with both Zn²⁺ ions, (ii) multiple polar interactions involving His122, Asp124, His189, Asn220 and Lys211, and (iii) extensive hydrophobic contacts with residues forming the surrounding pocket. These interactions collectively support a plausible and stable positioning of pinocembrin within the catalytic cavity of NDM-1.

Galangin, a flavonol structurally related to quercetin, has demonstrated potent antimicrobial and anti-inflammatory properties. Its antibacterial activity includes inhibition of drug-resistant strains of *S. aureus* at moderate concentrations, without cross-resistance to conventional antibiotics (Cushnie et al., 2005). Galangin is also known to potentiate the effect of β -lactam antibiotics by interfering with bacterial membrane permeability. In addition to its antimicrobial effects, galangin has been investigated for anticancer activity, showing the ability to induce apoptosis in malignant cells (Rampogu et al., 2021).

Other high-affinity compounds identified in this study, including chrysin (Naz et al., 2019), vestitol (Franchin et al., 2016), and caffeic acid phenethyl ester (CAPE), also display pharmacologically relevant properties. Vestitol and its isomer neovestitol, which are abundant in red propolis, have been reported to suppress biofilm formation and inhibit Gram-positive bacteria, with additional anti-inflammatory actions (Bueno-Silva et al., 2013). CAPE, a well-known derivative of

caffeic acid, has demonstrated a wide range of bioactivities including antimicrobial, antioxidant, and antitumor effects (Murtaza et al., 2014).

Collectively, the compounds identified in Ukrainian steppe bee propolis not only demonstrate promising computational binding affinities to NDM-1, but also possess well-documented biological activities that may enhance their potential in treating infections caused by β -lactam-resistant pathogens. Their multifunctional nature, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial properties, suggests potential roles as synergistic agents in combination therapies. These findings underscore the remarkable chemical diversity of propolis and its relevance as a natural source of enzyme inhibitors. In particular, the superior docking performance of pinocembrin and galangin highlights their promise as lead candidates for further pharmacological development. The structure-based virtual screening approach used in this study provides an effective framework for prioritizing bioactive scaffolds from natural products in the search for novel β -lactamase inhibitors.

4. Discussion

The present study combines chemical profiling and structure-based virtual screening to explore Ukrainian steppe bee propolis as a source of potential inhibitors of New Delhi metallo- β -lactamase-1 (NDM-1), a clinically critical enzyme driving resistance to β -lactam antibiotics. The integration of LC-MS/MS identification,

drug-likeness assessment, and molecular docking enables interpretation of the results within both a chemical and pharmacological context.

Chromatographic and mass-spectrometric analysis revealed that Ukrainian propolis is rich in flavonoids and hydroxycinnamic acid derivatives, including pinocembrin, galangin, chrysin, pinobanksin, vestitol/neovestitol, and caffeic acid esters. This qualitative profile is consistent with propolis compositions reported for temperate regions, yet also reflects regional botanical specificity, which is known to influence propolis chemistry and biological activity. The presence of multiple isomeric flavonoids underscores both the chemical diversity of the extract and the analytical challenges associated with unambiguous identification, highlighting the need for complementary techniques such as NMR for future studies.

Drug-likeness analysis demonstrated that all investigated propolis-derived compounds fall within favorable physicochemical space according to Lipinski, Veber, and Egan criteria. In contrast to clinically used β -lactamase inhibitors, which are highly polar and often require parenteral administration, the propolis compounds exhibited moderate lipophilicity and lower polar surface area. This distinction suggests improved potential for passive membrane permeability and oral bioavailability, characteristics that are desirable for adjunctive antimicrobial agents. Importantly, compliance with classical drug-likeness filters does not imply efficacy but supports the feasibility of further development.

Molecular docking against the NDM-1 crystal structure (PDB ID: 8I8F) revealed that several propolis-derived flavonoids displayed predicted binding affinities comparable to or stronger than those of established β -lactamase inhibitors within the same docking framework. Pinocembrin and galangin emerged as the top-scoring compounds, occupying the enzyme's active site in proximity to both catalytic Zn^{2+} ions. The predicted interaction patterns suggest a combination of metal-adjacent positioning, polar contacts with key residues (including His122, Asp124, and His189), and hydrophobic stabilization within the binding cavity.

Beyond docking affinity, the identified compounds possess documented antimicrobial, anti-inflammatory, and antioxidant properties. Such multifunctional activity may be advantageous in combination therapies, where β -lactamase inhibition could synergize with host-protective or antibacterial effects. However, it is important to emphasize that molecular docking provides only a predictive assessment of binding and does not directly measure enzymatic inhibition or antibacterial synergy.

Overall, the results support the hypothesis that propolis-derived polyphenols represent a chemically and pharmacologically relevant pool of scaffolds for further investigation. The combination of favorable drug-like properties and plausible interaction with the NDM-1 active site justifies subsequent biochemical validation,

including enzyme inhibition assays, metal-chelation studies, and microbiological testing in resistant bacterial strains.

5. Conclusions

This study demonstrates that Ukrainian steppe bee propolis contains a diverse set of polyphenolic compounds with physicochemical properties compatible with early-stage drug development. LC–MS/MS profiling identified flavonoids and hydroxycinnamic acid derivatives as dominant constituents, reflecting both the chemical richness and regional specificity of the propolis sample.

Structure-based molecular docking against New Delhi metallo- β -lactamase-1 revealed that several propolis-derived compounds, particularly pinocembrin and galangin, exhibit favorable predicted binding within the enzyme's active site. Their interaction profiles suggest proximity to catalytic Zn^{2+} ions combined with stabilizing polar and hydrophobic contacts. In parallel, drug-likeness analysis indicated that these natural compounds occupy a more balanced physicochemical space than many clinically used β -lactamase inhibitors, with implications for oral bioavailability.

Taken together, the findings indicate that Ukrainian propolis represents a promising natural source of bioactive scaffolds with potential relevance for combating β -lactam resistance. While the present results are based on computational

predictions, they provide a rational basis for targeted experimental validation and further exploration of propolis-derived compounds as adjunctive or lead candidates in antimicrobial drug development.

Abbreviations

ADME Absorption, Distribution, Metabolism, and Excretion

BLI β -Lactamase Inhibitor

CAPE Caffeic Acid Phenethyl Ester

ddH₂O Double-Distilled Water

HBA Hydrogen Bond Acceptor

HBD Hydrogen Bond Donor

HPLC High-Performance Liquid Chromatography

LC– Liquid Chromatography–Tandem Mass Spectrometry

MS/MS

MBL Metallo- β -Lactamase

MIC Minimum Inhibitory Concentration

MW	Molecular Weight
NDM-1	New Delhi Metallo- β -Lactamase-1
PDB	Protein Data Bank
PSA	Polar Surface Area
Ro5	Rule of Five (Lipinski)
TPSA	Topological Polar Surface Area
TFA	Trifluoroacetic Acid

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